

An Onboarding Checklist for Research Computing and Data Professionals

Gladys Andino
gka6a@virginia.edu
University of Virginia
Charlottesville, VA, USA

Scott L. Delinger
scott@altadel.com
Altadel Computing
Edmonton, AB, Canada

Jacob Fosso Tande
jfosso@ncsu.edu
North Carolina State University
Raleigh, NC, USA

Timothy Middelkoop
tmiddelkoop@internet2.edu
Internet2
Columbia, MO, USA

Claire Mizumoto
claire@ucsd.edu
University of California San Diego
La Jolla, CA, USA

David P. Reddy
davidreddy@sc.edu
University of South Carolina
Columbia, SC, USA

Michael D. Weiner
mweiner3@gatech.edu
Georgia Institute of Technology
Atlanta, GA, USA

April 26, 2024

1 Introduction

In this paper we present an onboarding checklist for Research Computing and Data (RCD) Professionals. RCD Professionals are individuals that work with researchers, students, and industry staff on the computing and data needs associated with their work or study. The terms Cyberinfrastructure (CI) and research information technology (Research-IT) are often used interchangeably with the term RCD; however, in this onboarding checklist we will primarily use the term RCD. More information about RCD can be found in[1].

RCD Professionals work in a wide variety of institutions, organizations, and teams with different structures. This onboarding checklist uses a consistent nomenclature to keep the presentation clear and general in nature. This should not be seen as an endorsement of this language but a means to communicate clearly. For universities, companies, institutions, etc., we use the term *organization*. Within an *organization*, an *RCD program* will contain RCD Professionals (e.g., an RCD center) working in one or more *RCD teams*. The *RCD program* is led by an *RCD program director* (often with the title of Director). The *new hire* is the RCD Professional that will be onboarded and will also be referred to as the new team member. The *new hire* will report to a *supervisor*, which could be a team lead, manager, etc. For checklist items that are specific to a role (such as a facing, student, or staff), the role will be indicated in bold; a more detailed description of the facings can be found in[2]. For some organizations there may be only a single *RCD team* within the *RCD Program*, and the *new hire* will report to the *RCD Program Director*; in some cases there may be a lone RCD Professional; and for others it may be a large collection of teams spread across the *organization*. In all these cases the checklist should provide a good starting point for onboarding new RCD Professionals.

This onboarding checklist is a result of the work by the Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC) Staff Workforce Development Interest Group[3] and the work during the 2023 RCD Nexus Day workshop on workforce development[4]. CaRCC is “an organization of dedicated professionals

developing, advocating for, and advancing campus [RCD] and associated professions” [5]. RCD Nexus is a National Science Foundation-funded Resource and Career Center within CaRCC that is focused on developing survey instruments and job family frameworks, defining career arcs, and developing best practices for career development for staff and student RCD professionals[6].

2 Onboarding Checklist

The onboarding process can be divided into four distinct phases that are *getting ready*, *first days*, *first weeks*, and *first months*. This onboarding checklist covers one-time onboarding activities specific to the RCD organization and does not include detailed organizational, divisional (information technology, office of research, or similar), or Human Resources (HR) onboarding and training. We also do not cover ongoing RCD-specific training that an RCD professional may do during their career. The following subsections contain the checklist with context.

2.1 Before the First Day – Getting Ready

The *getting ready* phase is for checklist items that may have long lead times ahead of their start date. Depending on the situation, some new hires may not have an RCD background and may request to be given background materials to help get them ready for their first day. Many of the details will be deferred to the first weeks.

Allocate space for the new hire: This may be part of the organizational onboarding process.

Order laptop and/or workstation hardware: This may be part of the organizational onboarding process. If appropriate, work with the new hire on any customizations or additional needs. Consideration should be given to the tasks associated with the role (compiling code, RAM and GPU requirements, mobility for presentations, multiple monitors, etc.)

Provide background materials if requested: Send any requested background learning materials (for example, if they are new to the organization’s HPC cluster scheduler but have used others in the past, point them to public documentation). This is particularly important for individuals coming from different backgrounds, for example enterprise IT, industry, etc.

Calendar major events: Provide calendar items that might affect the new hire soon after the first day for planning purposes. For example, if there are training sessions, conferences or other events that happen soon after the new hire’s arrival, communicate these dates and times. The new hire should also communicate important calendar items.

Collect schedule restrictions: For full-time **staff**, schedules may need to accommodate daily events like childcare drop-offs and pickups, eldercare, and the like. **Student** RCD workers may have these events as well, but also class schedules, break time, on-campus vs off-campus time, etc. Communicating organizational and team expectations around schedules and ability to accommodate the needs of individuals is crucial to a good onboarding experience for the new hire.

2.2 First Days – Big Picture, Elevator Pitches, and Essentials

The *first days* are about key information to help the new hire get acclimated. Big picture items (mission, vision, tenets) allow them to learn the culture and norms of the organization and how they, as individuals, fit into the larger picture. Essential items allow them to get connected to technology and to other people.

Welcome to your new job: Arrange for time with the new hire to welcome them to the team, and start them on the right path. This initial meeting should cover the checklist items immediately following this one and set follow-on meetings. It is important to recognize the different onboarding

needs of individuals; for example a new-to-organization hire vs someone already familiar with the organization.

RCD program mission and vision: Communicate the RCD program mission and vision and how it relates to the new hire and their position. Include the tenets of the program, and present the elevator pitch. This information could also be discussed in prescreening and in writing.

Define individual and team success: Explain what success looks like for the new hire in terms of big-picture goals (see previous point) and specific items, including metrics in general and specific Key Performance Indicators. More detailed expectations can be communicated at a later time. For new **student** hires, define success in terms of both work product and learning outcomes. [7]

Assign onboarding ambassadors: An onboarding ambassador is a colleague who will provide information and training, answer the new hire's questions, and help them gain comfort with the team. The ambassador may be different for each phase as the focus shifts from general information to detailed aspects of the role. For the *first months* checklist, ideally, this should be someone in a similar role who they can shadow while performing standard activities.

Introduce essential productivity tools: Introduce specific productivity tools that the team uses to communicate and get work done. These tools include email, messaging, ticket management systems, video conferencing, and project management systems. Role-specific tools (e.g., source control management) can be deferred to the *first weeks*. This introduction should also include what should not be used. For example, some groups or institutions may require the use of specific products due to policy and licensing or discourage or prohibit other tools. This is especially important for RCD systems and support provisions for sensitive data research (i.e., biomedical, defense, or sociological fields with personally identifiable information (PII)) in the event that private or sensitive data is included in discussion content while providing research support.

Provide external and internal documentation locations: Introduce essential external and internal documentation for reference. This may include documentation specific to the RCD team or the larger organizational group. Note: If numerous documentation sources exist, any "table of contents" with links to all the sources should be placed in an obvious location known to all staff. This can also include important status and dashboard information.

Invite to essential meetings (shared calendars and calendar invites): Invite the new hire to any essential meetings, such as regular one-on-one meetings with their manager, periodic team meetings, or casual meet-ups. Information on the typical locations of the meetings (in person, hybrid, or fully remote) should be shared for each meeting. Share the location of any meeting minutes that are maintained. Any shared calendars should be shared and calendar sharing permissions norms should be discussed. This is a good time to discuss how to initiate meetings, invitation content norms, etc.

Communication norms: Establishing clear communication norms is vital for seamless team interactions, encompassing guidelines for both internal and external channels. This includes defining suitable methods and tools for user communication and ensuring professionalism and coherence in user-facing interactions. Determining the extent to which this is discussed may be determined by the new hire's role. For example, researcher-facing communications are very different from responding to tickets in a ticketing system. Similarly, a systems-facing communication among technical peers is not the same as details (or summaries) for non-systems technical recipients. Internally, it is crucial to clarify when and how staff members can be contacted for efficient workflow management. Awareness of team members' remote work status or different time zones helps manage expectations.

Remote working norms: Communicate the expectations about working from home (offsite) versus onsite, and expected working hours. This includes team core hours when all members should be available for collaboration. For **students**, coordinate with class schedules to identify work hours and, as necessary, ensure coverage of key responsibilities.

Norms about taking leave: Whether illness, vacation, or other reasons including childcare or eldercare, team norms regarding coverage of duties, minimum concurrent staffing, and how the

team denotes being away such as entries in a team absences calendar should all be communicated and documented for reference. This may be in addition to any information communicated in the HR onboarding. Describing expectations regarding scheduled time-off, relative to other members of the team, calendar consideration, such as the beginning of the academic quarter/semester, and those major conferences where the RCD program members might have a large presence or heavy participation. If not provided by HR, institutional holidays and closures should be outlined.

Team introductions: Introduce the other members of the new hire’s immediate team, prioritizing people who will be initially working closely with the new hire. Reinforce any special information about how and when to contact them, including the direct supervisor and/or RCD Director. Share the organization chart and organizational structure of the functional “team” to identify avenues for support or communication. Consider a team-building activity like lunch or another opportunity for casual conversation. Depending on the size of the team, consider the extent to which this is done in the *first days* to avoid overwhelming the new team member. For **students**, the manager of student team members plays a key role in introducing students to staff members and fostering a collaborative team environment.

Workspace setup and facilities: If the new hire is designated to be onsite or hybrid, ensure they are granted physical access to their designated workspace or available hoteling space, including appropriate door access permissions or keys. Additionally, if not issued by the organization’s HR, provide essential equipment such as a computer and necessary access credentials to enable seamless integration into the working environment. Provide facilities and building tours as appropriate. For **onsite** new hires, tour the important aspects of their primary building(s) including restrooms, emergency exits, muster points in case of an emergency or building evacuation drill, and closest available parking locations and specific rules beyond those provided during the HR onboarding. For **students**, ensure that the student has access to staff credentials (groups or roles in directory services) as appropriate. If the student RCD team members work onsite and have determined space allocations different from staff spaces, explain workspace provisioning. For **systems-facing** or other new hires that require datacenter access, give a tour as a researcher would receive. Provide additional details, including specialized and safety equipment (server lift, testing equipment, hearing and laser eye protection), proper lifting techniques, and evacuation (fire suppression details). Communicate expectations on any mandatory occupational health & safety training necessary for the new hire’s work environment.

Overview of equipment, hardware, and services the team provides: Identify services the team supports, including clusters, other hardware, systems, middleware (including authentication tools, account management, and cybersecurity responsibilities), and software.

Plan the first weeks: Begin discussing plans for the first few weeks, such as training sessions and initial assignments to support provision or a project.

2.3 First Weeks – Deeper Dives: Team, Systems, Services

Broader introduction to RCD program structure should wait until the first weeks, once the new hire is familiar with their own immediate team. Once basic familiarity is established, help them begin to understand the greater organization and how the RCD program contributes to research and how the delivery of digital service and support can occur.

Other team building activities: Continue team-building efforts to integrate the new hire, including meals or casual activities such as games.

Campus tour: For onsite or hybrid employees, expand beyond the initial building tour to share landmarks from across the campus, such as the bookstore, local restaurants, and recreation amenities. Tailor this to the new hire, depending on their prior familiarity with the campus and locations they might need to visit in the future. If possible, give the new hire not in systems-facing roles a datacenter tour like a researcher would receive.

Visit and meet collaborators: Introduce frequent partners and collaborators beyond the RCD team, such as Research Administration, Libraries, and other IT units, either in person or virtually. Let the new hire know who to ask for help on different topics. Researcher-facing roles may focus on introduction to key researchers, however, introductions to teams managing other aspects of campus IT (such as cybersecurity) should not be reserved just for the systems-facing roles. In all cases, focus on engaging the new hire into networks appropriate to their delivery of services and support. The RCD program may be such that the researcher-facing role requires the greatest overall knowledge of partner services, while other more narrowly focused facings' roles may require fewer specific introductions.

Regular Check-ins: Set up regular check-ins at a higher frequency in the early stages to collect feedback from the new hire on how the onboarding is progressing and resolve uncertainties. Be sure to offer a clear opportunity for feedback on the onboarding process itself, to improve it for the future.

RCD annual cadence: Relate to the new hire how the RCD calendar may differ from an assumed cadence based on undergraduate instructional experience: spring may be busier with added requests from researchers as they plan for summer field work and ask for preparation assistance. Summer can be busy as graduate students may take fewer or no courses, leaving them more time for research. Being aware of the annual conference schedule for larger meetings such as Practice and Experience in Research Computing (PEARC)[8], or others will help to plan staffing levels during those weeks of the year. It is important to understand that heavier research activity times are often opposite of the academic/instructional peak times such that “Cautionary change windows” where systemic changes are limited or prohibited may not be in alignment. RCD training delivery in the form of “summer schools” or other periods may be scheduled with considerations for both research and instructional schedules.

IT and cybersecurity protocols: Cover formal security protocols, change management, and other formal complaint expectations and practices. In addition to the RCD programmatic security standards and methods, clearly define those directly related to the new hire’s work. For **students**, provide a clear progression of increased elevated access privileges as the student gains experience and demonstrates skills. For example, define the criteria a student employee must fulfill before gaining permission to enter user accounts or impersonate users to provide support.

Short term goals: Set expectations for the first few months, describing this period largely as a time to observe, ask questions (especially “why”), and learn processes. Set goals and timelines for the new hire to achieve a level of independent competency, focused on core responsibilities of the position. This timing may be accelerated for a new team member hired into a higher classification (assuming they bring more experience and knowledge). Include personal goals in the process.

Overview of important short- and mid-term projects: Familiarize the new hire with the RCD program’s current projects, the key partners or collaborators outside the RCD team, and the background behind the projects. Emphasis should be placed on the projects in which the new hire has a role, specifying their responsibilities in those projects, along with project schedules. Establish clear priorities among the projects, so that the new hire understands where their project and operational duties fit into the overall deliverables of the team and is not overwhelmed with attempts to understand details of other projects in which they do not have a role.

Team culture: Describe the team culture and share expectations and standards about interaction and collaboration within the team. In a hybrid or remote operation, ensure the new hire is aware of any social opportunities designed into the team’s work schedule, e.g., Friday afternoon social hour or the like.

Supervisor-employee relationship: Beyond HR supervisory best practices, an RCD program might include expectations for the relationship between the new hire and their direct supervisor. The establishment of rapport as the relationship develops might be built on foundational differences of a RCD program from enterprise IT and how measurable goals and accomplishments are more difficult to capture for RCD programs and RCD professionals. Support for research and researchers is often

very independent work and a solid foundation of communication and cooperation with the supervisor is necessary for the success of the new hire.

Institutional formal requirements: In addition to RCD program-specific required training, review any institutional requirements. This is a good time to describe performance appraisal methodology, format, and process in the organization or RCD program: for example, quarterly reviews with a formal annual performance appraisal, just annual appraisals, etc.

Further user setup: Provide access to additional systems and development tools not yet provisioned, including training on usage.

2.4 First Months – Details

For the remaining months, the onboarding activities are more detailed and are often specific to the new hire’s role. Some of the checklist items provide more depth in specific topics and others provide more detail about the broader background and context around the position. The final items develop a plan for continued professional development beyond the onboarding process.

Team building activity: Consider informal team building activities that include current team members. These may include local social events (campus or city events) or social activities at conferences such as dining. More formal team building activities with a professional facilitator may be valuable for multiple hires, team restructuring, or as an annual or other periodic gathering.

Attend researcher/student training sessions led by peers: If applicable, set expectations for the new hire to begin delivering training sessions in the future, perhaps at a one year anniversary or other appropriate time interval. Share training materials with the new hire across many training offerings so they can absorb training norms of the team, such as “we start from a Software Carpentry approach where we make no assumptions of the trainee’s background or current knowledge.”

Dashboards and tools: For **systems-facing** individuals, cover in-depth system monitoring tools, dashboards, configuration management, CI/CD, and other operational systems providing credentials when necessary. For **researcher-facing**, provide customer relationship management software access, networking monitoring tools, and any dashboard or other tools relaying data about research groups’ usage status, e.g., use of HPC systems showing trends or sudden changes, such as a local installation of Open XDMoD[9]. For **data-facing**, discuss available data management tools, research data repositories, data flow tools, and research data transfer monitoring dashboards, as applicable. For **software-facing**, refer to code repositories and any developer tools licensed by the team, unit, or institution and provide/discuss any authentication requirements.

Fit in the organization: Describe how the new hire and RCD program fit in the institution and the institutional mission, which provides context for decision-making and can contribute directly to RCD professional’s job satisfaction. If possible, review the RCD program’s strategic plan and communicate how it contributes to a larger effort, such as a research and innovation strategic plan or even an organization’s strategic plan. Enterprise IT employees in some cases are not given this top-down view of the meaning and value of their position and their work to the broader institution. Share team, department, and organization org charts along with functional org charts denoting how different units, both academic and service, fit into the organization’s operational model.

Funding and budget discussion: Communicate the budget cycle and its schedule, factors in play such as governmental funding and cost recovery, and greater effects like supply chain issues. Be as transparent as possible in sharing funding status for the RCD program and the department and how the RCD program may be affected by the larger organization.

Expand external team introductions : Continue and deepen introductions to additional groups and less frequent collaborators, beyond those introduced in the first weeks. Provide a list of individuals within units who are known to be important in the delivery of RCD services and support. This can be crucial to a new hire’s understanding of how the team effectively and efficiently

supports researchers. As appropriate, begin introductions to common vendor contacts.

Past work of the team: Summarize past work of the team and where to find reference information when needed. This may include annual reports, completed projects, and retired resources about which researchers may ask questions.

Introduction to CaRCC and the broader RCD resources and community: External RCD communities can provide valuable insight and structure for the new hire to gain expertise. Introduce CaRCC and other relevant organizations, such as Campus Champions[10] and US-RSE[11], as well as regional and national resources, such as ACCESS[12] and state and regional education networks (RENs). Clarify expectations for engagement in these communities. Include introductions to local or regional organizations, chapters, and collaborations, such as open data groups. Offer subscription to mailing lists and webinar series, e.g., the Cyberinfrastructure Engineers group (cybinf-engr@es.net)

Introduction to self-serve learning resources: Provide RCD-specific information for institutionally provided self-paced training subscriptions. Describe available training provided by the organization and any funding that may be available for training fees. Including any team experiences with the different training options may help to determine suitable engagement.

Develop a training and career development plan: Although understanding an RCD career trajectory may be better suited for subsequent discussions after the new hire has been on the team for some additional time, it can be helpful to begin introducing potential opportunities within the first months. RCD training opportunities and conferences, such as CyberAmbassadors[13], the University of Oklahoma Virtual Residency Program[14], Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing (PEARC)[8], Supercomputing (SC)[15], and the Linux Clusters Institute[16], can teach valuable skills and introduce the new hire to the RCD community as a source of ongoing support. Additionally, the paper “Understanding Factors that Influence Research Computing and Data Careers”[17], which describes how other RCD professionals have navigated their career, is of value to both the new hire and the supervisor.

Acknowledgements

The following people were instrumental in the running of the 2023 RCD Nexus workshop on workforce development, which inspired and provided materials for this paper: Betsy Hillery, Purdue University; Timothy Middelkoop, Internet2; Claire Mizumoto, UC San Diego; Anita Orendt, University of Utah; Tom Cheatham, University of Utah.

This work was supported in part by a National Science Foundation grant: OAC-2100003, an NSF-funded Cyberinfrastructure Center of Excellence (CI CoE) demonstration pilot — RCD Nexus. The authors would also like to acknowledge the broad community of volunteers who have contributed in workshops, working groups, and other activities over many years.

References

- [1] N. Berente, J. Howison, J. Cutcher-Gershenfeld, J. L. King, S. R. Barley, and J. Towns, “Professionalization in Cyberinfrastructure,” *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 2017.
- [2] RCD Professionalization Working Group, “Research Computing and Data Professionals Job Elements and Career Guide,” tech. rep., Zenodo, Apr. 2018.
- [3] “CaRCC Staff and Student Workforce Development Interest Group.” <https://carcc.org/staff-and-student-workforce-development/>, 2024.
- [4] P. Schmitz, C. Mizumoto, T. Middelkoop, and D. Siefert McCause, “RCD Nexus Day 2023 Final Report,” tech. rep., Zenodo, Nov. 2023.

- [5] “Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC).” <https://carcc.org/about>, 2024.
- [6] “RCD Nexus.” <https://rcd-nexus.org/about/>, 2024.
- [7] V. K. Narayanan, P. M. Olk, and C. V. Fukami, “Determinants of Internship Effectiveness: An Exploratory Model,” *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, vol. 9, pp. 61–80, Mar. 2010.
- [8] “PEARC Conference Series – Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing.” <https://pearc.acm.org/>, 2024.
- [9] J. T. Palmer, S. M. Gallo, T. R. Furlani, M. D. Jones, R. L. DeLeon, J. P. White, N. Simakov, A. K. Patra, J. Sperhac, T. Yearke, R. Rathsam, M. Innus, C. D. Cornelius, J. C. Browne, W. L. Barth, and R. T. Evans, “Open XDMoD: A Tool for the Comprehensive Management of High-Performance Computing Resources,” *Computing in Science & Engineering*, vol. 17, pp. 52–62, July 2015.
- [10] M. Brazil, D. Brunson, A. Culich, L. DeStefano, D. Jennewein, T. Jolley, T. Middelkoop, H. Neeman, L. Rivera, J. Smith, and J. Wernert, “Campus Champions: Building and sustaining a thriving community of practice around research computing and data,” in *Proceedings of the Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing on Rise of the Machines (Learning)*, (Chicago IL USA), pp. 1–7, ACM, July 2019.
- [11] J. C. Carver, I. A. Cosden, C. Hill, S. Gesing, and D. S. Katz, “Sustaining Research Software via Research Software Engineers and Professional Associations,” in *2021 IEEE/ACM International Workshop on Body of Knowledge for Software Sustainability (BoKSS)*, (Madrid, Spain), pp. 23–24, IEEE, June 2021.
- [12] T. J. Boerner, S. Deems, T. R. Furlani, S. L. Knuth, and J. Towns, “ACCESS: Advancing Innovation: NSF’s Advanced Cyberinfrastructure Coordination Ecosystem: Services & Support,” in *Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing*, (Portland OR USA), pp. 173–176, ACM, July 2023.
- [13] A. Briliyanti, J. Rojewski, T. J. Van Nguyen, K. Luchini-Colbry, and D. Colbry, “The CyberAmbassador Training Program,” in *Proceedings of the Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing on Rise of the Machines (Learning)*, (Chicago IL USA), pp. 1–6, ACM, July 2019.
- [14] H. Neeman, D. Akin, H. Al-Azzawi, K. L. Brandt, J. Brooks Kieffer, D. Brunson, D. Colbry, S. Gesing, A. Klimaszewski-Patterson, C. Mizumoto, J. A. Pine-Thomas, A. Z. Schwartz, H. Severini, M. Tanash, and D. Voss, “Cyberinfrastructure Facilitation Skills Training via the Virtual Residency Program,” in *Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing*, (Portland OR USA), pp. 421–428, ACM, July 2020.
- [15] “SC Conference.” <https://supercomputing.org/>, 2024.
- [16] D. Akin, M. Belgin, T. A. Bouvet, N. C. Bright, S. Harrell, B. Haymore, M. Jennings, R. Knepfer, D. LaPine, F. C. Liu, A. Maji, H. Neeman, R. Reynolds, A. H. Sherman, M. Showerman, J. Tillotson, J. Towns, G. Turner, and B. Zimmerman, “Linux Clusters Institute Workshops: Building the HPC and Research Computing Systems Professionals Workforce,” in *Proceedings of the HPC Systems Professionals Workshop*, (Denver CO USA), pp. 1–8, ACM, Nov. 2017.
- [17] S. Chaudhry, A. Pazouki, P. Schmitz, E. Hillery, and K. Kee, “Understanding Factors that Influence Research Computing and Data Careers,” in *Practice and Experience in Advanced Research Computing*, (Boston MA USA), pp. 1–9, ACM, July 2022.